

From Learning to Practice

Tailoring RDM Training Materials to Your Community

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Quick Start Guide: Top 3 Things to Know

1. Join our dedicated [Rocket.Chat channel](#) and post a “hello” message.
2. Work with other participants from your consortium to adapt existing generic RDM training materials for your discipline.
3. Then, as a team, prepare a short contribution for the wrap-up event.

About This Document

This guide is designed to support participants of the RDMTraining4NFDI Hybrid Event during the asynchronous homework phase.

Goal: adapt existing generic RDM training materials to your consortium’s discipline, and prepare a short contribution for the wrap-up event.

Step 1: Select Material to Adapt

- Decide within your consortium which module or sections are most relevant for your community from the provided training materials:
 - [Foundations of RDM for beginners](#)
 - [Foundations of RDM for trainers](#)
 - [Practical Data Protection in Research](#)
 - [Open Science](#) (Open Access and at least one other section)
 - [Python for beginners](#)
 - Python for Advanced:
 - [Introduction to Seaborn for Data Visualisation](#)
 - [Merge Data Frames With Pandas](#)
 - [Object-Oriented Programming](#)
 - [ISBN Cleaning Function](#)
 - [Git for beginners](#) (section 2. Getting Started with Git)
 - [Git for advanced](#)
 - [Galaxy Basics for everyone](#)
 - [FAIR Galaxy Training Material](#)
 - [Train-the-trainer workshop on DMPs](#) (section 3.2. Training modules and levels (p. 9))
 - [Didactics & Motivation](#)
 - [Data Sharing](#) (all sections)

Step 2: Map to Your Discipline

For each chosen module / section, identify:

- Typical challenges your community faces (e.g. ethical/legal, technical, cultural)
- Key disciplinary examples (e.g. datasets, file formats, workflows, repositories)
- Relevant standards, policies and guidelines specific to your discipline

 Hint: If you'd like inspiration on how to adapt training materials, you can find a helpful guide [here](#). Good examples of adaptation are shown on **slides 13–17**.

Step 3: Adapt the Exercises

- Modify 1-2 of the generic exercises to make them meaningful for your community. Example: instead of a general “find a trustworthy repository” task, adapt it to “choose between Repository A and Repository B commonly used in our field, and explain why.”

Step 4: Document Your Adaptation

Copy this document in your own workspace, and document your adaptation with the following information:

- Consortium
- Module / section chosen for adaptation
- Original training materials link
- Adaptations made (e.g. examples, exercises)
- Challenges encountered during adaptation
- Ideas for integrating into your training portfolio

Step 5: Prepare Your Wrap-up Contribution

- Summarize your adapted material in a short (5 min) presentation for the 11 December wrap-up session. You can share slides, a demo exercise, or simply walk through your adapted template. Feel free to use our Google [Docs](#) or [Slides](#) templates.

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